

Misleading statements about vitamin C and the common cold in article on treatments for common cold in children by Gill et al. (2024)

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Comment on:

Gill PJ, Onakpoya IJ, Buchanan F, Birnie KA, Van den Bruel A.

Treatments for cough and common cold in children.

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Gill et al. reviewed common cold treatments for children [1]. In Table 2 they refer to our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold [2] and state the summary of evidence as “*No consistent effect [of vitamin C] on the duration or severity of colds*”. The topic is not discussed any further in the text section.

In fact, in our Cochrane review we calculated that in placebo-controlled trials, regular >0.2 g/day vitamin C shortened the duration of colds in children by 14.2% (7.3 to 21%; $P = 0.00005$); Analysis 2.1.2 (Trials with children) [2]. Furthermore, our calculation is based on 14 comparisons, whereas Gill states in their table that the number of vitamin C studies in our review on was 7. Thus, in contrast to Gill’s statement, our meta-analysis found that there is a consistent beneficial effect of regular vitamin C administration on common cold duration in children.

Recently we extended the analysis of vitamin C on the severity of colds [3]. We did not separate children into a category of their own; however, six comparisons with children contributed to the analysis. On average common cold severity was reduced by 15% ($P = 10^{-6}$). The largest of the child trials was carried out in Sweden, with Ludvigsson et al. reporting that “absence from school” during common cold episodes was reduced in the vitamin C group by 18% (1 to 33%) [3,4].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The above findings are a result of regular vitamin C supplementation, which means administering the vitamin, for example, over the winter. There are no therapeutic trials on children, in which vitamin C is started after the onset of symptoms. Nevertheless, given the high frequency of colds in young children, regular administration of a cheap and safe vitamin may be reasonable in some situations, though therapeutic trials should be encouraged.

Long-term prejudices against vitamin C have been demonstrated [5,6]. Evidence has shown unambiguously that, in certain contexts, vitamin C is effective against the common cold. However, in mainstream medicine, the views on vitamin C and infections have been determined by eminence-based medicine rather than evidence-based medicine. We demonstrated significant bias in many influential papers on vitamin C. We also showed that many of these papers have been uncritically cited in textbooks and reviews, assuming that they are scientifically valid, when in fact many of them have serious flaws. Thus, prominent authors have referred to the papers without undertaking any critical appraisal themselves [5,6]. In line with such previous problems, we are concerned that Gill et al. dismissed the strong positive findings about vitamin C.

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